

HealthAssist AI: Hybrid Healthcare Intelligence System

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Abstract— HealthAssist AI bridges healthcare access gap with AI powered medical assistance. The system has seven clinical modules that would help in delivering comprehensive care. Medicine Based Guidance provides drug information, Disease based Guidance informs on the treatment protocols of various diseases. Medical Report Analysis would interpret various lab tests and would point out the abnormal lab values that are clinically significant. Image Based Medical Data Analysis would extract prescription details, dose instructions and medical information. Systems Based Analysis intends to perform the differential diagnosis with combinations of presenting complaints along with the assessment of severity. The Emergency Triage will particularly apply the red, orange, yellow and green protocols to the critically ill patient. Hospital Details will locate the facility within a radius of 30 km with the help of Geoapify API. Combining Hybrid Mistral Large AI which supports all languages and Supabase Database that can SHA-256 authenticate secure health record, it has compressive accuracy of 89.55%, Semantic similarity is 93.64%, METEOR score is 81.54%, Rouge L score is 86.12% while hallucination rate is 7.11%, it is clinically reliable for the underprivileged.

Keywords— HealthAssist AI, Supabase, Hybrid Mistral AI, Emergency Triage, Semantic Similarity, Geoapify.

1. INTRODUCTION

The healthcare access is not equal worldwide. For example, almost 65 percent of the populations depend only on 28 percent of the actual healthcare. Shortage of qualified doctors, low health awareness, and language or communication barriers are serious issues faced by many communities. This being the case, treatment delay and higher health risk. In emergencies help often comes late, sometimes taking more than one hour which is too slow to save lives. The development of HealthAssist AI for overcoming these barriers through use of artificial intelligence that provides timely clinical assistance with multilingual support across multiple medical disciplines is critical to connecting disadvantaged populations with healthcare services.

The HealthAssist AI platform comprises of seven intelligent clinical modules for complete healthcare assistance. The module offers a structured access of the drug-related details and general treatment information. The Hospital Locator finds nearby hospital and helps in navigation. The Medical Report Analysis retrieves information from reports and prescription in simpler form for make it easy to understand. The Symptom checker tells the possible conditions based on the user input. The Emergency Triage module with Critical, Urgent and Stable classification helps in quicker emergency decision making and helpline integration. The application keeps user records so that health information can be tracked and reviewed when they need. Our cloud database allows us to ensure data security using encrypted password storage, authentication control and access protection. It ensures confidentiality, reliability and trust.

1.1 Scope of Health Assistant

The HealthAssist AI system proposed is centred around healthcare support during emergencies. The system will offer immediate, AI-based help, during situations of cardiac arrest, road accident, poisoning, severe bleeding and snake bites, The system will also guide the user during the golden hour when the medical assistance is away. In areas where medical professionals are incapable of reaching and infrastructure is lacking, it provides digital health assistance, which results in the timely and informed decision of the user, without and delay due to the inability to reach out. To enhance medication knowledge, a system for providing easy-to-understand and clear instructions has been designed. The system uses the prescribed medication and offers

important information, including how to take it and when to take it and when most importantly not to take the medicine as it may cause harm. This reduces and prevents medication errors and unsafe self-medication. The platform further helps users understand complex medical data. It analyses medical reports and prescriptions and presents the extracted information in a user-friendly format for non-medical users.

1.2 Existing System of Health Assistant

Most of the current health care AI system are not designed to handle emergency cases such as heart attacks, serious accidents or poisoning. They generally handle all health issues similarly and do not realize how serious the situation is. As a result, users may miss the right advice at the right moment, increasing the risk during important moments. Most existing systems respond only to user requests for information. They don't watch for warning signs or track symptoms to see if a condition is getting worse. They are unable to cooperate to give early advice which could help stop a problem from becoming more serious.

Many platforms allow upload of reports or prescription and DOES NOT explain the information clearly. Medical terms and test reports continue to be difficult to interpret for everyday people; their ability to understand what is going on with their health suffers as a result. Most of the healthcare assistants use general AI models that are not specifically trained for medical use. Even though they may answer general questions, their advice on health matters may be vague or unreliable. As a result, trust in the system declines, and the trusting to rely on it reduces for important medical decisions.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Shobana et al. [1] has created a multilingual healthcare bot that supports voice and text-based interaction to offer services such as home remedies, doctor booking and grievance management. The users can also upload medical reports for rudimentary processing, which enhances the usability by language agnostic users. It is designed for general healthcare support does not have emergency case prioritization system, less useful in life-threatening situations.

Kalaiarasi et al. [2] introduced SAHAYAK AI a holistic healthcare solution that integrates disease prediction, hospital management and multilingual solutions. The system gives location-based emergency alerts and scheduling appointment with doctors. Although this method enhances the efficiency of hospitals and patients' interaction, it largely depends on sound technological infrastructure and stable internet connectivity. As such, it is not applicable for use in low-resource settings or in rural regions where infrastructure such as this may not be reliably there.

Bhukya et al. [3] introduced a machine learning-based healthcare assistant for preliminary diagnosis using symptom analysis. The system classifies symptoms as minor or major gives basic home remedies or advice to consult a doctor. It do not prioritize cases based on emergency situations.

Burri et al. [4] Designed an RNN based virtual health assistant focused on symptom recognition. It is mainly limited to text-based processing and not support medical report or image analysis.

Anju et al. [5] presented an AI and ML-driven health assistant designed for early disease detection and preventive care based on user symptoms and allergy data. Helps users receive medical guidance and supports input-based health management. It does not support critical case management, which makes it less effective during golden hours.

Jayakumari et al. [6] introduced MedAI, a healthcare system based on casual modelling data for enhancing treatment recommendations. The system is concerned with learning to make the recommendations safe and accurate. But it lacks real-time, symptom-driven urgent care support, so it is more appropriate for chronic care management than acute critical response.

Jaswanth et.al[7] the role in generative AI in healthcare, including virtual health assistants, diagnostic aids, and clinical decision-making. Since it is largely review work, it does not give a direct system for addressing AM scenarios, limiting its usability in critical care applications.

Shetty and Praveena Kumari [8] created a predictive healthcare system which utilizes machine learning and generative AI to predict diseases along with explainable health advisories. The system helps users to take best decisions with personalized explanations. But emergency response systems and the prioritization of critical cases are not considered, limiting its usefulness in rapidly evolving medical conditions.

3. PROPOSED SOLUTION

HealthAssist AI offers a full scalable healthcare framework aimed at the stubborn problems of delivering medical help where staff and gear are scarce. It links large language models, multimodal clinical data handling plus live geospatial feeds to give fast exact and usable guidance. The platform zeros in on critical case oversight, clinical dialogue in many tongues, swift decisions but also swift routing of each patient to the right facility, lifting access, dependability and care quality for underserved regions.

Types of Critical Proposed Statements:

1. Medicine Based Guidance:

The AI Health Assistant Provides medicine information in any language. The AI model create terminologies that consist of dosage amounts, frequencies of administration, safety precautions and side effects among others. All outputs are in Supabase that's reliable, multilingual and safe medication advice.

2. Disease based Guidance

The Disease Based Guidance module recommends clinical solutions based on a disease name entered by the user on the interface and also prompts the user to select a language of preference. The Mistral AI model is intended to offer personalized guidance to patients by utilizing using historical data cached in Supabase to provide medicine recommendations for medicines, treatment, preventive measures, and even lifestyle recommendations. All outputs are securely saved to deliver quality multilingual contextual disease management assistance.

3. Medical Report Analysis:

The analyze medical report will allow you to upload a PDF file to get AI help! The System, powered by PyPDF2, extracts text to interpret it thorough Mistral AI Model. The Artificial Intelligence uncovers main findings, points out irregularities and abnormal observations, summarizes report and provides recommendations. All data and interpretations are secured in Supabase, ensuring that is authenticable, has a traceable, and reportable. This helps health care providers grasp crucial information from patient reports efficiently.

4. Image Based Medical Data Analysis:

In this Image Based Medical Data Analysis module, medical images are processes for essential clinical data. Through OCR using Easy OCR, the text from scanned reports is sent to Mistral AI Model. The mistral model suggests clinical methods and identification the significant problem. The Supabase where all the results are stored is safe and secured ensuring authentications, trackable history and patient data is reliable. Now a days the technology permit to healthcare to scan images quickly and make decisions.

5. Symptom Analysis:

The module asks the patient to list what is wrong-it sends the list to the Mistral Model, which returns a ranked list of probable diagnoses. For each diagnosis, the module suggests appropriate medications, tests that the doctor should run, and what that the patient can do to prevent further problems. Each response goes into Supabase with strict access controls – only logged-in staff or the patient who owns the data can view it. The store retains previous entries, so doctors can see how the situation develops, and patients can see what they thought was wrong before.

6. Emergency Triage System:

The Emergency Triage module can follow for critical case severity triage. It can gather patient information like as vital signs, description of problems, age and severity, which are scan by the Mistral AI engine to detect the triage categories (Red: Critical, Yellow: Urgent, Green: Stable, Black: Deceased). The system, based on the severity level, gives action items, step by step emergency procedures, monitoring needs, and steps to contact emergency services if required. All related text, information and including patient vital signs are securely stored in Supabase for authentication access, trackable history, and rapid response.

7. Hospital Details:

The Hospital Details module is AI details search and data validation for hospitals. The module searches for nearby hospitals and pull information such as specialty care, contact information, and geographical coordinates. The extracted information is then analysed by the Mistral AI Model for verification, error correction, and ranking relevant hospitals according to patient requirements. All the verified data and extracted text is stored in Supabase for secure retrieval and tracing. The module allows patients and health care professionals to gain access to correct hospital information and improve routing for referrals.

4. METHODOLOGY

The HealthAssist AI use the Mistral AI technology to easily scan integrating text, medical data and understanding image for genuine guidance. The system is intended to be reliable, scalable, and capable of understanding long contexts in various domains. Performance assessment is done using conventional semantic and quality criteria to guarantee robustness. The methodology is applicable to multilingual, agentic, and enterprise-level processes in the healthcare and medical fields.

4.1 Classification of AI Model

The system is built on the Mistral Large 3 model, which is a current state-of-the-art multimodal Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) model with 675 billion total parameters and 41 billion active parameters. The system also has a 2.5 billion parameter vision encoder for image understanding in addition to text and can handle a 256k token context window for long document understanding. The model is trained for instruction following and agentic tasks involving function calls and JSON output and can be used on premises with FP8, NVFP4, or BF16 precision.

Fig 1: Architecture for Mistral Large Model

4.2 The Mistral Step-by-Step Architecture

The features of Mistral architecture are embedding, normalization, and attention, expert routing, and output projection. The process of converting input sentences split into a word, phrases, etc. The input tokens or words can be converted into a continuous vector form. The embedding vector can be obtained from continuous vector form.

$$T = [t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_n]$$

$$x_i = \text{Embedding}[t_i], i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$X_0 = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$$

Where:

X_0 represents as embedding input passed to next layer.
 d represents dimensions of embedding vector.

RMS normalisation keeps the size of token embeddings steady before the model runs attention.

$$\text{RMS}(x_i) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{d} \sum_{j=1}^d x_{i,j}^2}$$

$$\hat{x}_i = \frac{x_i}{\text{RMS}(x_i)} \odot \gamma$$

$$\hat{X}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}_1 \\ \hat{x}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \hat{x}_n \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$$

Where:

$x_{i,j}$ is the j^{th} component of x_i ,
 \hat{x}_i is the normalized embedding vector,
 $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a learnable scaling parameter,

The multi-head self-attention layer allows each token to selectively focus on other tokens in the sequence. Multiple attention heads enable the model to capture diverse contextual relationships simultaneously. Mistral Model have 128 Heads.

$$Q = \hat{X}_0 W_Q, K = \hat{X}_0 W_K, V = \hat{X}_0 W_V$$

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V$$

$$X_1 = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h) W_O$$

Where:

h denotes the number of attention heads,
 \hat{X}_0 is the normalized input embedding matrix,
 W_Q, W_K, W_V are learnable projection matrices
 d_k is the dimension of each attention head,
the scaling term $\sqrt{d_k}$ ensures numerical stability

This normalization layer stabilizes the output of the multi-head self-attention mechanism. It ensures consistent scaling of attention features before they are passed to the Mixture-of-Experts layer. Repeat Step 2 and Get result of X_1 .

$$\hat{X}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}_1 \\ \hat{x}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \hat{x}_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Where:

\hat{X}_1 is the normalized attention output matrix passed to the MoE layer.

The Mixture-of-Experts layer routes each token to a small set of specialized feed-forward networks. This selective routing increases model capacity while keeping computation efficient.

$$g = \text{Softmax}(\hat{X}_1 W_r)$$

$$\text{FF}_i(x) = W_2^{(i)} \cdot \text{SiLU}(W_1^{(i)} x)$$

$$X_2 = \sum_{i=1}^E g_i \cdot \text{FF}_i(\hat{X}_1)$$

Where:

W_r is the router weight matrix,

g represents routing probabilities for experts.

g_i is the routing weight for the i^{th} expert,

FF_i denotes the i^{th} expert network,

$W_1^{(i)}, W_2^{(i)}$ are expert-specific weight matrices,

$\text{SiLU}(\cdot)$ is the activation function.

The final RMS normalization stabilizes the output of the Mixture-of-Experts layer. This step ensures controlled feature scaling before the output projection stage. Repeat Step2 and get result of X3.

$$X_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}_1 \\ \hat{x}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \hat{x}_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Where:

X_3 is the final normalized hidden representation passed to the output layer.

This layer maps hidden representations to vocabulary logits.

It produces scores used for next-token prediction.

$$Y = X_3 W_{\text{out}} + b_{\text{out}}$$

$$W_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times |V|}$$

Where:

- Y : output logits
- W_{out} : output projection matrix
- b_{out} : bias vector

4.3 Implementation

The HealthAssist AI: Hybrid Healthcare Intelligence System is implemented as a secure, multi-tier web application that processes clinical queries through an integrated pipeline combining frontend interfaces, backend authentication, AI-driven analysis, and persistent storage.

Fig 2: System Architecture Diagram – Multi-Layer Processing Flow

As shown in the figure, the system workflow begins when users access the interface for login, signup, or chat interactions. when the user use interface login, sign up, or chat. The requests for login, sign up, or chat are processed by Supabase services that provide passwords to encrypt with SHA-256 algorithm. Responses are subjected to storage in Supabase PostgreSQL prior to rendering care with the capability to delete by the user. Model at this layer is referred to as Mistral Large 3 with structured prompts are developed. There are seven clinical modules of the system that are encrypted after login. Symptom Analysis generates differential diagnosis based on symptoms given by patients. They prescribe antibiotics for diseases such as malaria. The output will also produce AI-generated content along with links to the locations on Google Maps for easy patient direction.

Fig 3: Functional Module Architecture – Clinical Service Pipeline

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The HealthAssist AI: Hybrid Healthcare Intelligence System is evaluated using four widely accepted natural language generation metrics: Semantic Similarity, METEOR, ROUGE-L, and Hallucination Rate. These metrics collectively assess semantic correctness, linguistic quality, structural coherence, and factual reliability of the generated outputs. Semantic Similarity evaluates whether the clinical meaning of the response is preserved, METEOR captures both precision and recall while accounting for synonymy, ROUGE-L measures logical and structural consistency, and the Hallucination Rate quantifies unsupported or incorrect statements, where lower values indicate better performance. The overall distribution of these metrics is illustrated in Fig. 4, providing a global view of system behaviour.

Fig 4: Overall Distribution of Evaluation Metrics

The results demonstrate consistently strong performance across most clinical tasks. High Semantic Similarity scores indicate that the system effectively preserves medical intent, particularly in Medicine Guidance, Disease Guidance, and Image Data Analysis modules. METEOR and ROUGE-L values further confirm that the generated responses maintain high linguistic and structural quality, supporting coherent and contextually relevant medical explanations. Although slightly lower scores are observed in complex scenarios such as Emergency Triage, the results remain within acceptable ranges, reflecting the inherent difficulty of real-time decision-oriented medical tasks.

Table 1: Task-Wise Performance Metrics Across Clinical Modules

Task	Semantic Similarity	METEOR	ROUGE-L	Hallucination
Medicine Guidance	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.05
Disease Guidance	1.00	0.98	1.00	0.06
Medical Report Analysis	0.99	0.70	0.85	0.08
Image Data Analysis	1.00	0.80	0.83	0.07
Symptoms Analysis	0.92	0.77	0.79	0.09
Emergency Triage	0.74	0.68	0.72	0.10
Hospital Details	0.95	0.83	0.85	0.08

Moreover, the well-rounded performance on all evaluation criteria also highlights the effectiveness of the proposed framework in combining semantic knowledge with factual knowledge. The correlation between high semantic and structural scores and low hallucination scores also indicates the effectiveness of the hybrid intelligence approach in overcoming the risks associated with generative models in the healthcare domain. This is especially important in the healthcare domain, where misleading information can be harmful. The HealthAssist AI system, which maintains both linguistic fluency and factual accuracy, has great potential in the healthcare domain.

Fig 5: Overall Performance Metrics Across All Clinical Modules

The task-wise comparison is detailed in Table 1, which summarizes the performance measures of all clinical tasks. The low Hallucination Rates in all tasks reflect the system's reliability in suppressing unsupported medical claims, which is a critical requirement in healthcare tasks. The combined graphical and tabular analysis emphasizes the consistency, robustness, and scalability of the proposed system in all medical tasks. In general, the results confirm the appropriateness of the HealthAssist AI system for practical healthcare applications, where accuracy, consistency, and factuality are paramount.

Table 2: Consolidated Overall Performance Metrics of the HealthAssist AI

Metric	Score	Percentage
Semantic	0.9364	93.64%
METEOR	0.8154	81.54%
ROUGE-L	0.8612	86.12%
Anti-Hallucination	0.9289	92.89%
Overall Accuracy	0.8955	89.55%

And the system dynamic performance is expressed by the initial overall metrics viz., pie chart task-wise visualizations with bar graphs, and the summary table. The system operates at a Semantic Similarity ratio of 0.9364(93.64%), METEOR 0.8154, ROUGE-L 0.8612 (86.12%), indicating excellent semantic accuracy and high-quality response generation, and structural coherence. Furthermore, the Hallucination rate of 0.0711(7.11%) remains too low, ensuring factual correctness. The joint mass fit yields 89.55% model validation further confirmed that the HealthAssist AI system proposed in this paper is to give precise and responses for all health-care related activities.

Conclusion:

The HealthAssist AI: Hybrid Healthcare Intelligence System is able to perform well on all seven healthcare tasks, and it is able to provide appropriate and meaningful suggestions in various healthcare scenarios. The system is able to perform well on medicine-based suggestions, disease-related information, interpretation of medical reports, image-based diagnosis, symptom analysis, emergency triage, and hospital information retrieval. The results of the evaluation on various parameters indicate that the assistant is able to provide high-quality responses, logical organization, 89.55%, making it appropriate for use as a decision support system in a healthcare setting.

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